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The Contradiction between Economic Pragmatism and Romantic Sensibility in Jane Austen's *Sense and Sensibility* and *Emma*

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Abstract:

This article examines the contrast between economic pragmatism and romantic sensibility in Jane Austen's novels, particularly *Sense and Sensibility* and *Emma*. Austen provides a nuanced portrayal of how socio-economic pressures shape marital choices, women's autonomy, and romantic aspirations. Austen performs a thoughtful rendering of her character's conflicts and choices in her novels. The novel *Sense and Sensibility* depicts a contradiction between Elinor Dashwood and Marianne Dashwood. The characters Elinor and Marianne embody economic pragmatism and romantic sensibility, respectively. Elinor's steadfast integrity and prudence in financial matters stand in contrast to Marianne's idealistic quest for emotional authenticity. This contradiction highlights the economic limitations imposed on women's autonomy and socio-economic constraints that shape their choices and identities. The minor characters such as John Willoughby and Lucy Steele demonstrate the conflict between financial necessity and romantic idealism. In like manner, in *Emma*, the central character, Emma Dashwood, depicts the balancing act in negotiating societal expectations and romantic sensibility. In the early stages Emma embodies a practical approach, arranging matches based on social considerations. However, after her personal development and self-awareness, she begins to understand the importance of genuine emotional bonds. The minor characters in *Emma*, such as Jane Fairfax and Harriet Smith, depict the broader conflict between two seemingly opposite forces that

converge within the story. Austen's depiction of these characters provides a critique of the period's socio-economic standards, exhibiting the inherent struggle between financial considerations and personal happiness. Through close reading of the primary texts and the use of secondary sources, this paper calls attention to Austen's insightful observation of women's emotional and economic struggles in navigating their marriage. Additionally, this study inspects how these novels address women's position in the late 18th and early 19th centuries, examining the dichotomy between securing one's fortune and personal happiness.

Keywords: Economic pragmatism, Romantic sensibility, Societal expectations, Socio-economic pressures, Women's struggles.

Introduction

Jane Austen was the daughter of Reverend George Austen and Cassandra Austen. She was born on 16th December 1775, the seventh child of her parents. At the time of her birth, her family lived in Hampshire at Steventon Rectory. Jane Austen shared a deep bond with her only sister, Cassandra. She remained her closest friend and lifelong confidante. She received her early education at home. Her father's vast library enabled her to access a wide range of literature.

At the age of 19, Austen composed her first novella, *Lady Susan*, in an epistolary form. In the coming years, she began *Sense and Sensibility*, and it was first named *Elinor and Marianne*. *Pride and Prejudice*, earlier called *First Impressions*. Following the rejection of publication of *First Impressions*, she began *Susan* later developed into *Northanger Abbey*. In 1814, the novel *Mansfield Park* was published, and Austen began work on *Emma*. *Emma* was the last novel to be published before her early death, likely from Addison's disease. She wrote her final novel, *Persuasion*, amidst her deteriorating health. The first novel published in the

year 1811 was *Sense and Sensibility*, and the second novel was *Pride and Prejudice* in 1813. In 1818, posthumously, *Northanger Abbey* and *Persuasion* were published. Two unfinished works of Austen include *The Watsons* and *Sanditon*. Although Jane Austen at present is regarded as a celebrated novelist of England but, she was an anonymous author at her time. The major novels of Jane Austen were published in the early 19th century, while her works are deeply rooted in the literary traditions of the 18th century. Jane Austen is a transitional author as her works bridge 18th- century Enlightenment ideals and the 19th-century shift toward Romanticism and Realism. She was influenced by 18th-century authors such as Samuel Richardson, Frances Burney and adopted social critique, rationality in her works. At the same time, Austen anticipated Romanticism by including emotional depth and psychological complexity. Also, her realistic depiction of social structures and economic limitations foreshadowed the realism of the 19th century.

Jane Austen's novels centre on the plot of marriage. As William H. Magee argues, 18th and 19th- century novels often placed marriage as "virtually the only career then open to a woman" (198). However, rather than passively accepting the social framework, Austen "adapted it to her particular purpose in each novel", using courtship as a medium to critique social and economic limitations (Magee 207). Her personal life influenced her novel writing. Two of Jane Austen's brothers, Charles and Francis, were high-ranking Royal Navy officers, and their experiences influenced her depiction of naval officers in *Persuasion*. Though she never married but her short-lived romance with Tom Lefroy in her early twenties, which ended because of economic concerns, likely shaped her understanding that marriage is both a personal and economic decision, a recurring theme in her novels. As Meenakshi Mukherjee notes, Austen exposes "the economic anxiety that underlies the romantic veneer of the courtship ritual" (138). Unlike the Romantic writers of her time, Jane Austen deliberately

avoided sentimentality. She used free indirect discourse, a style of narration that incorporates the voice of the narrator with a character's inner thoughts.

Therefore, this paper, through the exploration of the conflict between economic pragmatism and romantic sensibility in her works, highlights Austen's critique of societal expectations. She also negotiates Enlightenment rationality and Romantic emotion, reinforcing her position as a transitional writer in literary history.

Socio-economic constraints

The Regency era (1811-1820) was marked by the limitations imposed upon women's economic opportunities and the presence of rigid gender roles. The woman's property and wealth were transferred to her husband upon marriage because the legal system operated under coverture. The inheritance laws favoured male heirs through primogeniture. This resulted in women's lack of financial independence and the need to secure their future through marriage. As William H. Magee in "Instrument of Growth: The Courtship and Marriage Plot in Jane Austen's Novels (1987) argues that 18th and 19th century novels often placed marriage as "the only career then open to a woman" (198).

In *Sense and Sensibility*, the sudden death of Henry Dashwood leaves his wife and daughters in a precarious situation. Mr. Dashwood was left with "no power of providing for those who were most dear to him, and who most needed a provision, by any division of the estate, or by any sale of its valuable woods" (Austen 6). The daughters and his wife were left with no legal claim to his property. The principle of primogeniture prioritizes inheritance to the eldest male. The Norland estate passes entirely to John Dashwood, who is Henry's son from his first marriage. This legal framework was designed under the pretence of protecting women. The women who relied on the benevolent protection of men were considered respectable. However, this legal structure traps women like the Dashwoods in a framework that constrains

their autonomy. The opening chapters of the novel depict the legal and economic hardships the Dashwoods need to confront. This indicates how these societal structures impacted the women's lives in early 19th-century England.

Unlike the Dashwood sisters in *Sense and Sensibility*, Emma Woodhouse in *Emma* is independent in terms of economic considerations. This independence allows her a rare privileged position in society as a woman to remain unmarried if she chooses. Emma Woodhouse asserts her financial independence by rejecting the societal expectations imposed on women, stating:

I have none of the usual inducements of women to marry. Were I to fall in love, indeed, it would be a different thing! but I never have been in love; it is not my way, or my nature; and I do not think I ever shall. And, without love, I am sure I should be a fool to change such a situation as mine. Fortune I do not want; employment I do not want; consequence I do not want: I believe few married women are half as much mistress of their husband's house, as I am of Hartfield; and never, never could I expect to be so truly beloved and important; so always first and always right in any man's eyes as I am in my father's. (Austen 82)

The estate of Hartfield, in which Emma resides, is neither entailed nor legally restricted in other ways. The impact of laws of inheritance in *Emma* is depicted through the situation of Frank Churchill and his romantic involvement with Jane Fairfax.

Frank Churchill's circumstance indicates the strict nature of inheritance laws. Mr. Weston, his father gave up to the affluent Churchill family after his mother's death. Frank had no legal claim to the estate, but he was raised as the estate's heir. This made him vulnerable to them as his inheritance depended on their preference. Frank Churchill's aunt imposed absolute authority over him to make sure he did not marry below his social position. This compelled

him not to disclose his engagement with Jane Fairfax. Jane Fairfax is an orphan with no fortune. She lacks security in terms of economic considerations and has no inheritance to depend on. In contrast to Emma Woodhouse, who is financially independent, Jane Fairfax needs to face the grim reality. She considers the profession of governess as her last resort. The work of a governess was exploitative in nature; well-educated but impoverished women needed to settle for that. They were required to sell their skills in return for low wages and little respect. In Austen's society, work was not a respectable path for women to gain monetary independence. A woman chose a profession only when marriage became unattainable. There were limited options for professions because of social and economic constraints.

The most common professions available to women in the early 19th century were governess, paid companions to wealthier women to provide company and assistance, teachers who offered young women a basic education in sewing, music, reading, and writing.

Although rare, some women chose to adopt writing as a profession. However, these women writers were required to use male pseudonyms or often published anonymously. They adopted this method to avoid social stigma. Writing could not be considered a reliable option for financial independence because of low income. Jane Austen chose writing as a profession and maintained a modest, anonymous literary career in order to adhere to the expectations of her social class. Women belonging to the lower class of society chose positions as cooks, maids, and housekeepers. These options were not for genteel women because they were expected to avoid physical labour. In the late 18th and early 19th centuries, many women faced poverty and dependence on relatives.

Jane Austen's novels highlight how important inheritance and marriage were for women's financial security and survival in society. In "Emma and Miss Bates: Early Experiences of Separation and the Theme of Dependency in Jane Austen's Novels", Margaret Moore points out Miss Bates' dependent nature : "And because she is also poor and stupid, she

is all the more dependent on the goodwill of others for the preservation of her self-esteem” (580). In Jane Austen’s novel *Emma*, Miss Bates faces financial hardship because of a lack of income and her unmarried status. Due to her lack of inheritance, she depends on the goodwill of others - particularly, the wealthy members of Highbury society, such as Emma Woodhouse and Mr. Knightley. Emma initially disregards her as tedious and silly and “remind Miss Bates of her personal inadequacies and her lowly status” (Moore 580). Later, Emma learns to appreciate her humility and kindness. “Without the Box Hill episode, Emma would have been a less important book” (Moore 585). In Jane Austen’s other novel *Persuasion*, features the character of Mrs. Smith, formerly Miss Hamilton, is a widow and an old school friend of Anne Elliot faces financial deprivation after her husband’s death. Mrs Smith’s character highlights the precarious position widowed women had in Austen’s society without financial independence.

In *Sense and Sensibility*, John Willoughby’s actions are heavily influenced by financial constraints and inheritance law. These socio-economic constraints shape his choice in love and marriage. Willoughby is the presumed heir to his aunt, Mrs. Smith of Allenham. “Mr. Willoughby had no property of his own in the country; that he resided there only while he was visiting the old lady at Allenham Court, to whom he was related, and whose possessions he was to inherit” (Austen 45-46).

However, he loses his inheritance because of his reckless behaviour. In Chapter 31 of *Sense and Sensibility*, Colonel Brandon reveals to Elinor Dashwood that Willoughby had seduced Eliza Williams, Brandon’s young ward and left her “in a situation of the utmost distress, with no creditable home, no help, no friends, ignorant of his address!” (Austen 198). On learning about this scandal, Mrs. Smith disinherits Willoughby, and he loses the financial security needed to prioritise romantic attachment in marriage. To secure his future through marriage, he chooses to marry Sophia Grey, a wealthy heiress.

Tension between romantic aspirations and financial realities

Jane Austen's novels consistently depict this tension between romantic aspirations and financial realities. Inheritance laws, rigid social structures, and gendered economic constraints shaped the lives of the characters. Austen's protagonists value romantic attachment, long for genuine companionship, and aspire to marry for emotional connection rather than economic considerations. However, societal expectations and socio-economic constraints compel them to navigate difficult choices.

In *Sense and Sensibility*, Marianne Dashwood represents the romantic ideal. Marianne believes in romantic love as an all-consuming passion. She falls for John Willoughby, and initially they appeared to be compatible with each other. As the narrator describes Marianne's rejection of concealment in her notion of romantic attachment:

Marriane abhorred all concealment where no real disgrace could attend unreserve; and to aim at the restraint of sentiments which were not in themselves illaudable, appeared to her not merely an unnecessary effort, but a disgraceful subjection of reason to common-place and mistaken notions. Willoughby thought the same; and their behaviour, at all times, was an illustration of their opinions. When he was present she had no eyes for anyone else. Everything he did, was right. Every thing he said, was clever. If their evenings at the park were concluded with cards, he cheated himself and all the rest of the party to get her a good hand. If dancing formed the amusement of the night, they were partners for half the time; and when obliged to separate for a couple of dances, were careful to stand together and scarcely spoke a word to anybody else.

(Austen 54)

The moment of tension begins when Willoughby suddenly departs for London without any promise of his return. She was unaware of the economic pressures influencing

his decision. Eventually, he decides to marry wealthy Miss Grey for financial security after he loses his inheritance. Later, Willoughby confides to Elinor with a heavy heart about his relationship with his wife, “She does not deserve your compassion. -She knew I had no regard for her when we married” (Austen 307). Willoughby confesses to Elinor “Tell her of my misery and my penitence-tell her that my heart was never inconstant to her, and if you will, that at this moment she is dearer to me than ever” (Austen 307). He acknowledges that his focus on the accumulation of wealth through marriage has resulted in loss of happiness from his life. The resolution of the tension occurs when Marianne ultimately marries Colonel Brandon. Colonel Brandon, a man who offers both affection and stability. Marianne undergoes personal development and realises the importance of stability in marriage. She experiences a shift in perspective from a marriage based on unrestrained romantic passion one that balances both economic considerations and affection. Though it seems Elinor Dashwood and Marianne Dashwood embody opposing ideals, one of sense and the other of sensibility, in reality, they possess both qualities.

While Elinor is pragmatic and outwardly composed, she experiences emotions deeply and suffers privately. This indicates that she is not devoid of sensibility. Elinor’s emotional depth can be identified when she expresses herself to her sister Marianne, and her knowledge of Edward Ferrars’ prior engagement with Lucy Steele. Elinor understands that she would be forever separated from Edward Ferrars and endured the pain of this thought in silence, and suffered the punishment of their attachment in solitude. Elinor has endured the pain of suffering alone-“The composure of mind with which I have brought myself at present to consider the matter, the consolation that I have been willing to admit, have been the effect of constant and painful exertion” (Austen 247). As Ruth ApRoberts identifies in “Sense and Sensibility, or Growing Up Dichotomous” (1975) that “the two girls, Elinor, though obviously

representing sense, has feelings that are strong, and Marianne, though obviously representing sensibility, has a distinguished intellect" (ApRoberts 355).

In *Sense and Sensibility*, Elinor Dashwood suppresses her emotions and prioritises rationality, knowing Edward Ferrars is bound by duty to marry Lucy Steele. Unlike Marianne's uninhibited passion, Elinor expresses herself through measured words that reflect her inner struggle. However, the tension is resolved unexpectedly the moment when Elinor learns that Edward is freed from his engagement because Lucy Steele has married his brother, Robert Ferrars. This is a moment of emotional release for her : "Elinor could sit it no longer. She almost ran out of the room, and as soon as the door was closed, burst into tears of joy" (Austen 335).

In *Emma*, Emma Woodhouse's marriage to Mr. Knightley is marked by Emma's pride, emotional upheaval and eventual self-awareness. Initially, Emma viewed marriage as a social contract and focused on the importance of economic considerations associated with marriage. Emma considers herself above marriage because of her financial independence. She believes her independence exempts the need to find a husband. However, her interference in other's decision-making regarding marriage-particularly Harriet Smith, forcing Emma to realise her misconceptions and her inner desires.

Throughout the novel, Emma assumes she has the ability to orchestrate matches and takes pride in that. This belief blinds her to her own emotions and leads her to manipulate Harriet Smith to reject Robert Martin. Emma persuades Harriet that Robert Martin is not a suitable choice because he lacks refinement. Emma shares her view with Harriet Smith regarding the man "Mr. Martin looked as if he did not know what manner was" (Austen 31). Emma mistakenly believes Mr. Elton to be a more suitable match for Harriet Smith. However, she realises her mistake only when Mr. Elton reveals his intentions towards Emma Woodhouse. Emma feels humiliated and astonished hearing Elton's words, "I am very much astonished, Mr.

Elton. This is me! you forget yourself-you take me for my friend-any message to Miss Smith I shall be happy to deliver; but no more of this to me, if you please” (Austen 123). This is a turning point when Emma realises, she cannot control romantic attachment as easily as she thought. However, Emma’s misjudgement continues as she encourages Harriet’s growing emotions for Frank Churchill. The knowledge of Frank Churchill’s engagement to Jane Fairfax and the eventual understanding that Harriet desires to marry Knightley and not Churchill. Emma is forced to realise her true feelings and understands her heart’s yearnings for Mr. Knightley. She grapples with jealousy when she mistakenly believes Knightley may have romantic feelings for Harriet, “It darted through her, with the speed of an arrow, that Mr. Knightley must marry no one but herself” (Austen 382). Instead of controlling the situation, Emma experiences powerlessness. She realises her actions are guided by her misjudgement, “How inconsiderate, how indelicate, how irrational, how unfeeling had been her conduct! What blindness, what madness, had led her on” (Austen 382). The moment of deep mutual understanding is witnessed when Knightley confesses his love for Emma, his words- “If I loved you less, I might be able to talk about it more. But you know what I am.-You hear nothing but truth from me” (Austen 403). Unlike the financially driven matches in Austen’s novels such as Charlottle Lucas and Mr. Collins’ marriage in *Pride and Prejudice*, Emma and Knightley’s union is based on genuine affection, a marriage of equals. Emma navigates her marriage by ensuring that she does not leave Hartfield, indicating her decision to marry is not of submission rather a balanced arrangement. In Jane Austen, Meenakshi Mukherjee points out, “In Jane Austen’s novels, there is a constant tension between a woman’s need to exercise choice in order to define herself as an individual and society’s demand that she should conform” (Mukherjee 42).

Importance of class in Austen's society

The rigid class structure played an important role in shaping individual choices in marriage in early 19th-century England. Social mobility was restricted, and marriage was one such way through which one could improve one's social standing and financial stability. Jane Austen, in her novels, critiques the class barriers that hinder personal freedom in marriage. England in the Regency period was strictly hierarchical. The social classes were strictly divided into the aristocracy, the gentry, the middle class, and the working class. In Austen's world, marriage was a means of social preservation. The societal expectation for men was that for financial security, one could choose marriage and become financially stable, even though they had other professions to select from in order to be financially stable. Wealthy men could marry for romantic attachment, but those who depended on one's relative for inheritance and with uncertain prospects encountered disinheritance if they married imprudently. On the other hand, women needed to depend on marriage for financial survival, social standing, and to avoid destitution.

In an essay titled "Class" by Juliet McMaster in the book *The Cambridge Companion to Jane Austen*, McMaster puts forth the existence of class difference in Austen novels as "of course a fact of life for Austen, and an acute observation of the fine distinctions between one social level and another was a necessary part of her business as a writer of realistic fiction" (McMaster 115). Lisa Hopkins in "Jane Austen and Money" argues that *Pride and Prejudice* depicts the importance of status and class in Austen's society. The marriage of Charlotte Lucas to Mr. Collins is not only for economic reasons, "but because by doing so she acquires an importance in society which would otherwise be perpetually denied to her" (Hopkins 77). In Chapter 29 of the novel *Pride and Prejudice*, Mr. Collins puts forth Lady Catherine's perspective on social hierarchy. Mr. Collins refers to Lady Catherine de Bourgh and says, "She likes to have the distinction of rank preserved" (Austen 158). Lady Catherine de

Bourgh's intention to preserve rank reveals the deep-seated class consciousness of the late 18th and early 19th centuries. The period when social status played an important role in the functioning of relationships in forming one's personal worth. Even Lady Catherine de Bourgh attempts to forbid any potential engagement of Elizabeth Bennet with Mr. Darcy because of Elizabeth's inferior position in terms of social rank and wealth.

“The Highbury of Emma is close to presenting a microcosm of Austen's social world” (McMaster 118). In *Emma*, Emma Woodhouse is financially independent and initially dismisses marriage because of her social standing and autonomy. She attempts to find a socially advantageous match for Harriet Smith, “the natural daughter of somebody” (Austen 23). Harriet Smith's parentage is unknown, and she received her education from Goddard's school. The prominence of class in society is evident through Harriet's unsuitability for gentry suitors because of her lack of respectable birth. Although Emma views Harriet as suitable and worth improving, “those soft blue eyes and all those natural graces should not be wasted on the inferior society of Highbury and its connections” (Austen 24). Disregarding the societal expectations, Emma attempts to elevate Harriet Smith's social position by pairing her with Mr. Elton, a clergyman. Emma's hopes get demolished when she understands her misjudgements regarding Mr. Elton's liking for Harriet Smith. In chapter 15, Mr. Elton comments on the idea of marrying Harriet Smith- “Everybody has their level; but as for myself, I am not, I think, quite so much at a loss, I need not so totally despair of an equal alliance, as to be addressing myself to Miss Smith” (Austen 125).

Ultimately, Harriet accepts the match that is socially suitable and provides emotional fulfilment. Her engagement with Robert Martin, a respectable and hardworking farmer, shows her adaptability within the class-conscious society. Emma acknowledges the suitability of Robert Martin in chapter 55: “She had no doubt of Harriet's happiness with any good-tempered man; but with him” (Austen 55). Through the story of Harriet Smith, Jane

Austen critiques the rigidity and superficiality of class divisions because of their interference with genuine human connections. Also, Austen depicts how a woman's social standing, financial security significantly limit her options in marriage. In *The Cambridge Companion to Jane Austen*, it is mentioned by Juliet McMaster that some of Austen's characters "depends on the retail trade for its luxuries, its status symbols, often for its very food and drink. Mrs Allen in *Northanger Abbey* can think of nothing but her clothes; Robert Ferrars in *Sense and Sensibility* brings his whole personality to bear in the choice of a toothpick-case" (McMaster 126). Through Austen's novels, she critiques the idle manner of living of upper-class people of her time and their condescending attitude toward tradesmen and the working class. In *Sense and Sensibility*, Fanny Dashwood epitomises class arrogance. She convinces her husband that providing financial assistance to his step-mother and half-sisters would be excessive on their part and also, she mentions "if you observe, people always live for ever when there is any annuity to be paid them" (Austen 12).

Fanny Dashwood projects no sense of familial duty in her treatment of Elinor, Marianne and their mother and considers them as social inferiors. Mr and Mrs John Dashwood's marriage functions on shared values of pride, concern for appearances. This leads to Elinor and Marianne's limitations in marital prospects because of diminished dowries. Later, Elinor Dashwood marries Edward Ferrars, and Marianne Dashwood marries Colonel Brandon, negotiating both economic security and emotional attachment in marriage.

The marriage of Augusta Hawkins and Mr. Elton in *Emma* represents how financial ambition and social pretensions overshadow emotional connection. Through this satirical example, Austen critiques her society where the mercenary approach to marriage becomes the primary motive in forming marital relationships. Mr. Elton, the ambitious vicar in Highbury, initially aims for Emma Woodhouse, whom he finds beautiful. Emma is also wealthy, she is the daughter of a landowner, which meets his desire to marry someone above his social

position. However, when Emma does not accept his proposal, he immediately reorients his ambitions. He marries Augusta Hawkins, “in addition to all the usual advantages of perfect beauty and merit, was in possession of an independent fortune, of so many thousands as would always be called ten” (Austen 170). Nigel Nicolson in “Jane Austen and the English Class System” describes the nature of Augusta Hawkins as a “detestable type of social climber whom Jane Austen must often have encountered” (179). Nicolson also adds, “she takes short cuts to intimacy; she shows off; she drops names. She allows Emma to understand that in marrying Mr. Elton, the local vicar, she is doing him a great favour, because she has money and he has very little” (180). Mr. Elton and Augusta Hawkins’s marriage is rooted in mutual self-interest.

The concern of class is also evident in the novel, *Northanger Abbey*. Catherine Morland is welcomed by General Tilney, believing that she is an heiress. When it comes to his knowledge that she is not, he expels her without any explanation. This action of General Tilney reveals the hypocrisy of the upper class, where mercenary concern plays a vital role in negotiating marriage. However, Henry Tilney’s stand against his father’s materialism allowed him to negotiate both emotional fulfilment and economic considerations in his marriage. Through this novel, Austen presents a subtle critique of class rigidity.

In Austen’s other novel, *Mansfield Park*, she critiques the rigid class system and the limitations on women’s autonomy in her society through Fanny Price. She upholds moral integrity instead of choosing to marry because of social status and wealth. She chooses to deny Henry Crawford’s marriage proposal even if he is charming and holds a privileged position in society. Ultimately, she marries Edmund Bertram, which reflects her negotiation between romantic love and societal expectations.

Conclusion

This paper has attempted to examine the contradiction between economic pragmatism and romantic sensibility in Jane Austen's novels, particularly *Sense and Sensibility* and *Emma*. Through the close reading of the novels, it can be well understood that Jane Austen has not portrayed the two forces as opposites but rather their entanglement within the structure of marriage. The characters can achieve emotional fulfilment only when they navigate economic considerations and societal expectations.

The study reveals that the characters in Jane Austen's novels need to confront the economic realities of her time before they can achieve a romantic resolution. For instance, in *Sense and Sensibility*, Elinor Dashwood displays emotional maturity when faced with Edward Ferrars' lack of economic stability. Also, her sister Marianne Dashwood undergoes personal development and understands that romantic attachment alone cannot sustain a relationship in a society where economic stability determines security. In *Emma*, Emma Woodhouse's failed attempts in match-making make her self-aware, and she begins to recognise the value of emotional connection in romantic relationships. This self-awareness allowed her to understand the compatibility between Harriet Smith and Robert Martin, also her match with Mr. Knightley. Existing scholarship has provided a groundwork for these interpretations as Lisa Hopkins' study on Jane Austen and the influence of the broader movement of Romanticism offers the idea of true happiness' association with valuing the emotional connection. Meenakshi Mukherjee's identification of marriage as a recurring theme in Austen's novels and through which Austen's critique of the limitations in women's autonomy. Also, Juliet McMaster's study examines the importance of class in Austen's society and how the rigid class structure influences the courtship plots.

This study is based on these foundational studies. This article indicates that Austen does not disregard the institution of marriage rather depicts it as a site of both agency and

limitation. This study also adds to the previous academic findings on Jane Austen's works by depicting the manner Austen depicts the experience of inner conflict in her characters such as Elinor Dashwood, Marianne Dashwood, Emma Woodhouse, and even in minor characters such as Harriet Smith, Jane Fairfax. In order to represent the act of negotiation between economic pragmatism and romantic sensibility in Jane Austen novels. In her novels, Jane Austen does not idealise romantic sensibility in marital relationships, instead her narratives, display the importance of both sensibility and sense.

Therefore, Jane Austen's novels expose the intersections of romantic attachment and economic considerations, choice and submission to external forces, personal fulfilment and societal expectation. She portrays marriage not as a result of personal happiness rather a social construct shaped by socio-economic constraints. By portraying the contradiction between economic pragmatism and romantic sensibility within marriage with critical insight, Jane Austen questions the socio-economic standards of her time.

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